

Techniques Used In String Matching For Network Security

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Abstract : String matching also known as pattern matching is one of primary concept for network security. In this area the effectiveness and efficiency of string matching algorithms is important for applications in network security such as network intrusion detection, virus detection, signature matching and web content filtering system. This paper presents brief review on some of string matching techniques used for network security

Keywords : String, pattern, Filtering, honeypot, instruction, signature, network telescope

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